

Language and the Arts

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- The role of language in literature, music, and other art forms
 - Language and creativity
 - Language and aesthetics
 - Language and performance

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Annotation: Since language is not a natural phenomenon, its place is determined within social phenomena. However, at this point, we need to understand how it is related to other social phenomena. At the moment, the following question stands transversely: What are the similarities and differences between language and other social phenomena? We see the commonality of language with other social phenomena in the fact that society cannot develop without language, it is considered the key to spirituality and culture for society. Language is fundamentally different from other social phenomena according to the laws of its historical development and its function. We are fully convinced of this when we compare it with the legal, religious, and political views of society. This article is about language and art.

Key words: Culture, Creole languages, Pidgin languages, thought, art.

In fact, the political, religious or legal views of society members coexist with each historical stage of society's development (feudalism, capitalism) and its requirements, but language does not have such a feature. He always serves all members of the society equally, regardless of their political, religious and legal views. This, in turn, indicates that it is not a superstructure of the language base, because it is a phenomenon that has been living for thousands of years. Therefore, it will be understandable to all members of society. In addition to the above, it should also be said that language and culture cannot be directly equated. Because culture is an ideology according to its original meaning (A.Reformatsky, 16), and language serves any ideology in the same way. However, the language of each nation requires its national culture, in fact, it is an integral part of national culture. In other words, the culture of a nation is reflected in its language.

We can see the role of language in society in the fact that it is a tool of communication between people. However, it should not be understood that it can be a tool for language production. Some linguists try to equate it with a production tool (H. Marr). Of course, it is difficult to agree with such a crazy idea. A production tool produces a product, and it takes on a certain shape. Language, on the other hand, does not produce anything, it does not even have a physical appearance; it only has a structure and a system. It is through these system symbols that people exchange ideas with each other. This encourages reflection on thinking with language. Of course, the relationship between language and thinking is very integral. But they are not common occurrences. We can see it in the following: Language is the achievement of society, it is polished for centuries and lives for centuries.

Thought grows and changes faster than language, and at the same time, it cannot live without language. Thought without language cannot enter the sphere of communication between people. The laws of language are studied in linguistics, and the laws of thinking are studied in logic. However, language and thought are twin phenomena that are inextricably linked with each other, and language cannot function without thought, just as there is no thought without language.

The real use of language in society is undoubtedly directly related to the speech process. Speech activity, in turn, has two aspects:

1. Individual - psychic.
2. Objective - social.

The individual-psychic aspect of speech activity, in our opinion, does not require an explanation. Because in the process of communicating with members of society, a person is always in the midst of his inner experiences and the expression of his goals. In a word, the psyche of the speaker is inextricably linked with speech activity. However, based on the above thoughts and considerations, we cannot say that human speech has an absolutely individual character, in fact, it also has a social character depending on the environment in which it occurs and how it is addressed to someone. A person who speaks a certain language has mastered the same vocabulary and grammatical rules of that language. This indicates the social character of speech.

Language is a symbol of the nation's spiritual wealth, image and unity. Each nation is distinguished from other nations by its national identity and culture. In this, without a doubt, his language also appears as a manifestation of his culture. In fact,

the importance of the language in the development of a nation's culture, its historical traditions, values, and memory is incomparable. Language, as an important part of culture, reflects national culture in the process of communication. It is known that language can be a component of culture, its weapon, language is an expression of the spirit of culture and a unique way of culture existence. At this point, the Honorable President Sh. Mirziyoyev said, "The Uzbek language, one of the oldest and richest languages in the world, is a symbol of our national identity and independent statehood, a priceless spiritual wealth for our people. "Whoever wants to feel all the grace, charm and power of the Uzbek language, and its limitless possibilities, should listen to the songs of our Munis mothers, our thousand-year-old epics, our immortal articles, and listen to the magical songs of our Bakhshi and Hafiz." - once again prove that language and culture are inextricably linked.

Moreover, a language belonging to a nation lives and survives with that nation and people. Every nation has its own nature, living conditions, traditions, culture and art, and of course, every nation has its own motherland, family, and its dearest and proudest mother tongue. . Just as there is no river without water, there is no nation without language. For a person, the more valuable his motherland, parents, and family are, the more precious and sacred his mother tongue is. For this reason, linguistics always focuses on the issue of the interrelationship of language and culture, the unity of the nation. attention has been paid to the problems of normalization of speech, which is a part of its own custom, tradition, culture, and compliance with laws and regulations. As a result of long-term study and analysis of the relationship between language and culture, new aspects of such sciences as general linguistics, literary studies, psychology, philosophy have been opened, and they are linguistic and cultural studies, communicative linguistics, cognitive

linguistics, gender linguistics, ethnolinguistics, neurolinguistics, sociolinguistics. , psycholinguistics, mentallinguistics, cognitive linguistics, interlinguistics (translation from one language to another language), synchronic and diachronic linguistics, macro- and microlinguistics, computer linguistics are the basis for the formation and development of modern sciences, and create a basis for conducting scientific research in modern directions of linguistics .

It is natural to encounter different opinions about the process of describing the relationship between language and culture, because the interaction of these two concepts is extensive and has been in the center of attention of scientists for several years. Summarizing the results of previous and current studies, language and culture form a whole.

References

1. S. Usmanov. General linguistics. T., 1972.
2. T.A. Amirova, B.A. Olkhovikov, Yu.V. Rozhdestvensky. Ocherki po istorii linguistic. M., 1975.
3. N.A. Baskakov, A.S. Sodikov, A.A. Abduazizov. General Linguistics T., 1979.1 Introduction to Linguistics. Handbook Kholmonova. Z.T.T 2000
4. Introduction to Linguistics M. Iriskulov 1992 Indiana University 5. Dadaboyev H. A Linguistic Theory and Methodology T 2004
6. Introduction to Linguistics. M. Iriskulov 1992 Indiana University